

**AVAILABILITY AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LIVESTOCK IN SELECTED AGRO ECOLOGICAL REGIONS OF
MAHARASHTRA STATE**

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Abstract

The present study entitled “Availability and productivity of livestock in selected Agro Ecological Region of Maharashtra State” was undertaken by conducting survey among 450 respondents from selected three AER, in each AER two districts were selected. Seventy-five sample from each district were surveyed. In one AER 150 samples collected, hence total 450 samples from 3 AER were studied. The finding revealed that in Deccan plateau cent per cent of families had buffalo, ox, goat and poultry. In Central highland majority of the families had cows and in Eastern plateau majority of the families had poultry. Number of animals in Deccan plateau it was seen that majority of the families were having 1-2 number of cow, buffalo, ox, goat and poultry respectively. In Central highland majority and equal per cent of families had 1-2 number of cows, ox and goats. Fifteen per cent families were having 3 and more number of poultry. Eastern plateau majority of the families were having 1 -2 number of ox, poultry and cow respectively. In Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get milk from cow as by product. In Deccan plateau, majority of respondent get milk from buffalo as a byproduct. In Central highland and Eastern plateau respondents get only milk as a byproduct from buffalo. Regarding types of by products from livestock goat it was noticed that in Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get milk from goat. With respect to poultry it was noted that in all the three plateau majority of respondents get meat as a byproduct. Maximum productivity from the livestock it was found that in Deccan plateau from cow respondents get maximum productivity in summer season (38 %.) In central highland and Eastern plateau respondents get maximum productivity from cow in winter season (25 %). With respect to livestock buffalo, goat and poultry in all the three plateau i.e in Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get maximum productivity in winter season.

Key words : Livestock, productivity

Introduction

Livestock plays an important role in Indian economy. About 20.5 million people depend upon livestock for their livelihood. Livestock contributed 16% to the income of small farm households as against an average of 14% for all rural households. Livestock provides livelihood to two-third of rural community. It also provides employment to about 8.8 % of the population in India. India has vast livestock resources.

The livestock provides food and non-food items to the people. The livestock provides food items such as Milk, Meat and Eggs for human consumption. India is number one milk producer in the world. It is producing about 176.34 million tones of milk in a year (2017-18). Similarly it is producing about 95.22 billions of eggs, 7.70 million tonnes of meat in a year. The livestock products such as milk, meat and eggs are an important source of animal protein to the members of the livestock owners. The per capita availability of milk is around 375 g / day; eggs is 74 / annum during 2017-18. The livestock also contributes to the production of wool, hair, hides, and pelts. Leather is the most important product which has a very high export potential. (Nada 2023).

According to Patel (2023) Livestock is the backbone of rural India, playing a crucial role in sustaining the livelihoods of millions of rural households. With agriculture being the primary occupation in rural areas, livestock rearing complements farming activities and contributes significantly to rural economies. Livestock, including cattle, buffalo, sheep, goats, and poultry, provide various essential resources for rural communities. Milk and dairy products are vital sources of nutrition and income, while draught animals help in ploughing fields and transporting goods. Additionally, meat and poultry offer a source of protein and generate income through sales. In rural India, where mechanization may be limited, livestock is an invaluable asset that offers resilience and stability to households during times of economic uncertainty. It also empowers women in rural areas who often take care of small-scale animal husbandry activities.

Food security in many countries is at stake. Livestock system is viewed as tools of poverty alleviation, employment and income generation and behave as an insurance agency and risk coverage agency in the time of failures of cropping system or during

agricultural off season when no work is found for household members (Khan and Iqbal 2011).

Objectives

1. To know maximum productivity and income generated from livestock of selected AER
2. To know types of by product getting from livestock

Materials and Methods

Based on climatic factors, soil properties and physiographic settings, three different agro-ecological regions were selected i.e. Deccan Plateau, Central High Land and Eastern Plateau. Selection of the villages in each AER were based on the demographic, socioeconomic and ecological data elicited through secondary data and baseline survey. In each AER two districts were selected. Seventy five sample from each district were surveyed. In one AER 150 samples collected, hence total 450 samples from 3 AER were studied. Survey was conducted to collect the information on Livestock/Animals, types of by product from livestock, season wise maximum productivity and income generation from livestock. The data collected was then tabulated and interpreted.

Results and Discussion

Information on Livestock/Animals is presented in table no. 1. It is clear from the table that in Deccan plateau cent per cent of families had buffalo, ox, goat and poultry followed by cow (40 %). None of the family had sheeps. About Central highland it was noticed that majority (30 %) of the families had cows followed by ox 23 per cent, poultry 22 per cent and goat 19per cent. It was observed that in Eastern plateau majority of the families (43 %) had poultry followed by ox (37 %), cow (26 %), goa(22 %)and buff(6 %).

Regarding number of Livestock/Animals in Deccan plateau it was seen that majority 33 per cent, 72 per cent, 73 per cent, 71 per cent & 73 5 per cent of the families were ha 1-2 number of cow, buffalo, ox, goat and poultry respectively. About Central highland majority and equal per cent i.e. 25 per cent of families had 1-2 number of cows, ox, and 14 per cent of the families had 1-2 number of goats. Fifteen per cent families were having 3 and more number of poultry. In Eastern plateau majority 33 per cent, 28 per cent and 25 per cent of the families were having 1 -2 number of ox, poultry and cow respectively.

With regards to getting types of by products from livestock is shown in table no. 2. Regarding cow it was found that in Deccan plateau,

Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get milk from cow as by product. None of the respondents getting curd, buttermilk, butter, ghee and cheese as a by product from cow.

Getting types of by products from livestock buffalo it was found that in Deccan plateau, majority of respondent get milk from buffalo (32 %). Equal percentages (2 %) get curd and buttermilk, 3 per cent get ghee as a by product from buffalo milk. In Central highland and Eastern plateau respondents get only milk as a by product i.e. 1 per cent and 6 per cent respectively.

Regarding types of by products from livestock goat it was noticed that in Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents (26 %, 20 % & 17 % respectively) get milk from goat as a by product. Meager percentage of respondents from Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau get meat as a by product (4.6 %, 6.8 % & 6.5 % respectively). With respect to poultry it was noted that in all the three plateau respondents get meat as a by product.

Maximum productivity in which season is depicted in table no. 3. If we see the maximum productivity from the livestock it was found that in Deccan plateau from cow respondents get maximum productivity in summer (38 %) followed by winter (6 %) and rainy season (2 %). In central highland and Eastern plateau respondents get maximum productivity from cow in winter (25 %) followed by summer season (16 % & 8 % respectively) and rainy season (11 % & 7 % respectively).

With respect to livestock buffalo, goat and poultry in all the three plateau i.e in Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get maximum productivity in winter season. Income generation from livestock is presented in table no. 4. It was observed that in Deccan plateau income was not generated from the cow milk though they have cow. Respondents use the milk at their home. In Central highland majority (14 %) of the respondents generate income through milk of cow between Rs.1000/- to Rs.5000/- followed by 3 percent respondents generate income of Rs.10,000/- to more. While in Eastern plateau only 3 per cent of respondents generate Rs. 1000/- to Rs. 5000/- from milk of cow. Regarding generation of income from buffalo milk it was seen that Rs 1000/- to Rs. 5000/- were generated in all the three plateau (5 %, 0.66 % and 2 % respectively). In Deccan plateau only 3 per cent respondents generate income of Rs. 10,000/- to more. From livestock goat respondents from all the three plateau generate income between Rs.

1000 to Rs. 5000/- i.e. 2 per cent, 5 per cent and 3 percent respectively. Regarding poultry it was seen that respondents from Deccan and Eastern plateau did not generate income from poultry, but in central highland majority (5 %) of respondents generate Rs. 1000/- to Rs. 5000/- from poultry followed by 1 per cent generate Rs. 10000/- to more income

Conclusion

In Deccan plateau cent per cent of families had buffalo, ox, goat and poultry. In Central highland majority of the families had cows and in Eastern plateau majority of the families had poultry. Number of animals in Deccan plateau it was seen that majority of the families were having 1-2 number of cow, buffalo, ox, goat and poultry respectively. Central highland majority and equal per cent of families had 1-2 number of cows, ox and goats. Fifteen per cent families were having 3 and more number of poultry. Eastern plateau majority of the families were having 1 -2 number of ox, poultry and cow respectively.

Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get milk from cow as by product. In Deccan plateau, majority of respondent get milk from buffalo as a by product. In Central highland and Eastern plateau respondents get only milk as a by product. Regarding types of by products from livestock goat it was noticed that in Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get milk from goat. With respect to poultry it was noted that in all the three plateau respondents get meat as a by product.

Maximum productivity from the livestock it was found that in Deccan plateau from cow respondents get maximum productivity in summer season (38 %) In central highland and Eastern plateau respondents get maximum productivity from cow in winter season (25 %) With respect to livestock buffalo, goat and poultry in all the three plateau i.e in Deccan plateau, Central highland and Eastern plateau majority of respondents get maximum productivity in winter season.

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Table 1 Description of livestock / Animal

Description of Livestock/ Animal		Frequencies and percentages of Farm Women Based on different Agro ecological Region		
Sr. No.	Description of Livestock /Animal	Deccan Plateau (n=150)	Central Highland (n=150)	Eastern Plateau (n= 150)
	1. Cow	60 (40.0)	45 (30.0)	39 (26.5)
	2. Buffalo	150 (100)	0.7 (1.0)	9 (6.0)
	3. Ox	150 (100)	35 (23.0)	56 (37.0)
	4. Goat	150 (100)	29 (19)	33 (22.0)
	5. Sheep	Nil	Nil	Nil
	6. Poultry	150 (100)	34(22.0)	65 (43.5)
1	Cow			
	1-2	50 (33)	38 (25.0)	38 (25.0)
	3-More	5 (3.0)	19 (12.5)	2 (1.5)
2	Buffalo			
	1-2	109 (72.5)	1 (0.62)	8 (5.5)
	3-More	4 (2.5)	1 (0.62)	0.8 (0.5)
3	Ox			
	1-2	110 (73.0)	38 (25.6)	50 (33.5)
	3-More	3 (2.0)	5 (3.12)	5 (3.5)
4	Goat			
	1-2	107 (71.5)	22 (14.3)	20 (13.5)

	3-More	5 (3.5)	14 (9.3)	13 (8.5)
5	Sheep			
	1-2	Nil	Nil	Nil
	3-More	Nil	Nil	Nil
6	Poultry			
	1-2	110 (73.5)	19 (12.5)	43 (28.5)
	3-More	2 (1.5)	23 (15.0)	23 (15.0)

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages

Table 2. Type of By product from livestock

Livestock	Deccan Plateau (n=150)	Central Highland (n=150)	Eastern Plateau (n= 150)
Cow			
1. Milk	72 (48)	56 (37.5)	40 (26.5)
2. Curd	Nil	Nil	Nil
3. Buttermilk	Nil	Nil	Nil
4 Butter	Nil	Nil	Nil
5. Ghee	Nil	Nil	Nil
6. Cheese	Nil	Nil	Nil
Buffalo			
1. Milk,	34 (32.33)	2 (1.25)	9 (6.0)
2. Curd	3 (2.0)	Nil	Nil
3. Buttermilk	Nil	Nil	Nil
4. Butter	3 (2.0)	Nil	Nil
5 Ghee	5 (3.33)	Nil	Nil
6. Cheese	Nil	Nil	Nil
Goat			
1. Milk,	40 (26.66)	31 (20.66)	20 (17.33)
2. Meat	7 (4.66)	10 (6.87)	10 (6.5)
Poultry			
1. Milk	Nil	Nil	Nil
2. Curd	Nil	Nil	Nil
3. Buttermilk	Nil	Nil	Nil
4. Butter	Nil	Nil	Nil
5. Ghee	Nil	Nil	Nil
7- Meat	2 (1.33)	8 (5)	7 (4.5)
8- Egg	3 (2.0)	34 (22.5)	59 (39.0)

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages

Table 3. Maximum productivity in which season

Name of the animal	Deccan Plateau (n=150)	Central Highland (n=160)	Eastern Plateau (n= 200)
Caw			
1.Summer	57 (38)	25 (16.87)	12 (8)
2. Winter	9 (6)	38 (25.6)	38 (25)
3. Rainy	4 (2)	17 (11.8)	11 (7)
Buffalo			
1.Summer	16 (10.66)	0.9 (0.625)	7 (4.5)
2. Winter	28 (18.66)	1.82 (1.25)	9 (6)
3. Rainy	19 (12.66)	Nil	2.3 (1.5)
Goat			
1.Summer	3 (2.0)	12 (8.75)	3.8 (2.5)
2. Winter	5 (3.33)	17 (11.8)	17 (11)
3. Rainy	5 (3.33)	6.5 (4.37)	6.8 (4.5)
Poultry			
1.Summer	Nil	16 (10.62)	14 (9)
2. Winter	3 (2)	35 (23.75)	56 (37)
3. Rainy	Nil	15 (10)	20 (13.5)

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages

Table 4. Income Generation from livestock

Name of the animal	Deccan Plateau (n=150)	Central Highland (n=150)	Eastern Plateau (n= 150)
Caw			
1000-5000	Nil	22 (14.66)	5 (3)
10,000 -More	Nil	5 (3.33)	Nil
Buffalo			
1000-5000	8 (5.33)	1 (0.66)	3 (2)
10,000 -More	5 (3.33)	Nil	Nil
Goat			
1000-5000	4 (2.66)	8 (5.33)	5 (3)
10,000 -More	Nil	3 (2)	2 (1.5)
Poultry			
1000-5000	Nil	8 (5.33)	Nil
10,000 -More	Nil	2 (1.33)	Nil

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages